

TECHNOLOGY OF TEACHING COMMUNICATIVE LISTENING IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Annotation: The technology of teaching communicative listening in foreign language classes is a current direction in the methodology of teaching foreign languages, aimed at developing in students the ability to effectively perceive and understand oral speech in a foreign language in various communicative situations. The abstract is devoted to the analysis of modern technologies and techniques used to develop listening skills, as well as consideration of their effectiveness in the context of a communicative approach to teaching foreign languages. The work will consider such aspects as the selection of authentic materials, the use of interactive exercises, the use of information technology, as well as the role of the teacher in the process of teaching listening.

Keywords: listening training, communicative approach, foreign language, educational technologies, authentic materials, role of the teacher.

Introduction: In today's world, speaking a foreign language is an important skill that opens up many opportunities. One of the key aspects of language learning is listening, which allows you to understand and perceive speech in a foreign language. A communicative approach to teaching listening contributes to the development of communication skills and information perception.

Despite the fact that many schoolchildren have trouble in mastering foreign speech listening skills due to insufficient development of speech hearing and understanding of language structures, modern technologies offer effective tools to solve this problem. The use of authentic audio materials, such as podcasts, allows students to adapt to different accents and dialects, which promotes deeper immersion in the language environment. [1]

For the comprehensive development of language competencies of primary schoolchildren, we recommend combining various methodological techniques, including: communicative methods that contribute to the formation of communication skills; training exercises for automating language structures; information and receptive methods aimed at developing listening and reading skills; and test tasks to assess student achievements. [3]

Modern pedagogy requires future teachers not only to have deep theoretical knowledge and mastery of methodological techniques, but also to develop a wide range of personal qualities that allow them to successfully adapt to a dynamically changing educational environment and effectively solve pedagogical problems. [2]

Technology plays a key role in modern language education, offering innovative tools for developing listening skills. Interactive platforms, audiovisual materials and virtual classrooms create an immersive language environment that promotes effective learning. Technology provides access to authentic audio materials, allowing students to practice listening skills in real-world settings and develop cultural competence.

Many technology tools are easily accessible and allow students to self-pace their learning, promoting independence and responsibility.

Technology tools often offer interactive elements such as games and quizzes that make the learning process more fun and motivating.

Some tools offer personalized learning programs tailored to the individual needs of students, allowing them to effectively work on their weak areas.

Technology tools can provide instant feedback on listening exercises, allowing students to track their progress and make timely adjustments to their work.

Technologies employed in teaching listening skills can be categorized into audio and video formats. The quality of audio materials can differ, affecting pronunciation accuracy, speech clarity, and the authenticity of the listening experience. [4]

Listening is a complex process that includes:

- ❖ Retention of sound information: Retention of sounds in memory for further processing.
- ❖ Prediction: Determining the likely continuation of a statement.
- ❖ Using past experience: Comparing new information with existing knowledge.
- ❖ Creating mental images: Translating words into visual images.
- ❖ Internal pronunciation: Pronouncing words silently for better understanding.
- ❖ Chunking speech: Separating individual words and phrases for easier understanding. [5]

Conclusion: The technology of teaching communicative listening is an effective tool for developing students' language skills. It helps not only to improve the understanding of foreign speech, but also to develop communication skills, which makes the process of learning a language more interesting and productive.

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